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Chemical Investigation of Indian Medicinal Plants Possessing Anticancer Activity : Roots of *Euphorbia tirucalli* Linn.

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EUPHORBIA tirucalli Linn. (Euphorbiaceae), a woody climber, is widely cultivated in Indian

gardens for decorative purposes. The juice of the plant is useful in abdominal troubles, tumors, asthma and leucorrhoea¹. The milky latex is vesicant, rubefacient, purgative and carminative². The root of this plant is reported to possess anticancer activity³. The stem and milky latex of the plant have been examined for a number of compounds by different workers⁴⁻⁶. But roots of this plant have not been investigated for their chemical constituents. This is the first report on chemical examination of the roots of this plant.

Experimental

The air dried powdered roots of the plant were extracted with light petroleum ether (60-80°) under reflux. The yellow-green extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to get a resinous mass. This semi solid mass was fractionated into ethanol soluble (*Fraction 1*) and ethanol insoluble (*Fraction 2*) portions.

Fraction 1 was separated into five compounds, A, B, C, D and E by column chromatography using silica gel G as adsorbent in the solvent system benzene-ether (19 : 1).

Three compounds, F, G and H have been separated from fraction 2 on silica gel column in the system cyclohexane : ethyl acetate (4 : 1).

All the above compounds were identified by co-tlc and their identification have been confirmed by their spectroscopic studies with authentic references (Table 1).

The co-carcinogenic activity of the root of this plant is due to the presence of diterpenephorbol and resiniferonol derivatives.

TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS ISOLATED FROM ROOTS OF *Euphorbia tirucalli* LINN.

Sl. No.	Compound	hR _f value		Methods of identification	Ref.
		Observed	Authentic		
A.	24-Methylene cycloartenol	19	20	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 122°, m.m.p., ir, pmr and ms.	7
B.	Euphorbol	36	35	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p., ir, pmr and ms.	8
C.	Euphorbol hexacosanoate	70	70	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p., ir and ms.	9
D.	n-Hexacosanol	56	56	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p. and ir.	10
E.	12-Deoxyphorbol-13-O-phenylacetate-16-O- α -methyl butyrate-20-acetate	70	71	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, pmr and ms.	11
F.	Tinyaxoxin	30	30	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, uv and ms.	✓ ¹²
G.	Taraxerone	86	86	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, m.m.p. and ir.	12
H.	20-O-Acetylrresiniferonol-9,13,14-orthophenyl acetate	32	32	(α) _D ²⁴ ± 0°, ir, pmr and ms.	✓ ¹⁴

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Phytochemical Investigation of *Aesculus indica* Linn. and *Fragaria indica* Andr.

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AESCULUS indica Linn. (Hippocastanaceae)¹ is a large deciduous tree, used as folk medicine in various ailments² while *Fragaria indica* (Rosaceae)³ is a small perennial herb and said to be astringent and diuretic. Literature revealed that although some phytochemical work^{4,5} has been done on the leaves of *A. indica*, no such work has yet been reported on *F. indica*. We now report the results of systematic chemical examination of the stems of *A. indica* and the whole plant of *F. indica*.

The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the stems of *A. indica* upon chromatographic analysis over alumina yielded a compound in the petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1:1) mixture eluate which, after repeated crystallization from acetone, afforded colourless plates, m.p. 65-67°, [$\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 2945, 2825, 1450, 1370, 735 and 725 cm^{-1}].

It was identified as *n*-hentriacontane by direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample.

The concentrated chloroform extract of the defatted stems of *A. indica* was subjected to systematic chromatographic analysis over silica gel. The benzene eluate furnished a solid, (M^+ , 414), m.p. 133-36°. It responded positive to Liebermann-Burchardt test for sterol and was characterized as β -sitosterol by m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with authentic sample.

Further elution of the column with benzene-chloroform (1:1) yielded a solid, $C_{15}H_{30}O_2$ (M^+ , 340), m.p. 205°(d); $\nu_{\max}$ 3320 (-OH), 1720, 1605, 820 cm^{-1} (coumarin). On hydrolysis with 4% H_2SO_4 it yielded an aglycone, $C_{15}H_{26}O_4$, m.p. 276° identical with aesculetin (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir, with authentic specimen)⁶ and D(+)-glucose (identified by paper chromatography with authentic sample) and was characterized as aesculin by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir and nmr spectra with authentic sample⁶.

Later fraction of benzene-chloroform (1:1) eluate gave another compound, crystallizable from methanol-ethyl acetate (1:1) mixture in pale yellow leaflets, m.p. 180-82°. It yielded an aglycone, identical in all respects with quercetin and L-rhamnose (identified by paper chromatography) on hydrolysis and was finally identified as quercetin through comparative studies (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic specimen of quercetin⁷.

Fragaria indica: The concentrated petroleum ether (60-80°) extract of the whole plant of *F. indica* was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°) furnished two compounds; one having m.p. 80-82° (M^+ , 438) and the other, m.p. 135-36° (M^+ , 414). These two compounds were identified as triacontanol and β -sitosterol, respectively by comparative studies (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

Fraction eluted with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1:1) yielded a triterpene, $C_{30}H_{50}O$, (M^+ , 426) [α]_D+27° ($CHCl_3$), m.p. 210-12°, $\nu_{\max}^{\text{KBr}}$ 3235; acetate, m.p. 214°, identified as lupeol by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with authentic sample⁸.

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (60-80°)-benzene (1:2) yielded another triterpene, m.p. 258-60°, (M^+ , 426) characterized as friedlin through the preparation of its DNPH, m.p. 295-8° (d) and m.m.p. and co-ir with authentic specimen⁹.

Lastly, elution of the column with petroleum ether-benzene (1:3) also yielded a triterpene, m.p. 198-200°, (M^+ , 426); $\nu_{\max}$ 3425 cm^{-1} (broad, hydroxyl); acetate, m.p. 240-42°, characterized as β -amyrin through direct comparison (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc) with authentic sample¹⁰.